

Supplementary Material

Data processing and analysis.

Only unique records per grid cell were retained in the dataset (*Ae. aegypti* and imported dengue cases), applying a spatial buffer of 200–400 m around occurrence points. Pseudo-absence points were randomly generated across the study area, excluding buffered areas surrounding presence records, and were subjected to a strict environmental filter (temperature < 10°C and elevation ≥ 2,500 m). All covariates were extracted for both presence and pseudo-absence locations.

The modeling workflow consisted of five sequential stages:

1. Train–test dataset partitioning. Datasets were randomly split into a training (80%) and testing (20%) subsets using stratified sampling based on the presence or absence status. Exploratory data analysis (EDA) assessed missing values, outliers, predictors correlations (correlation matrices and principal component analysis-PCA), class balance and variable distributions.
2. Preprocessing. Highly correlated predictors ($r > 0.80$) were removed. Remaining variables were centered and scaled, and class imbalance was addressed through up-sampling to achieve a presence-to-absence ratio of 1:0.9.
3. Model training and tuning. Two gradient boosting algorithms were evaluated: LightGBM and XGBoost. Models were trained using 10-fold spatial blocks cross-validation with two repetitions. Performance was assessed using sensitivity, area under the ROC curve (AUC), and the true skill statistic (TSS). Hyperparameter were optimized through grid search (Tables 4–5).
4. Model evaluation. Models were internally evaluated using the same-year training and testing data sets, and prospectively validated to assess spatial and temporal stability, respectability. Model performance was assessed using sensitivity, the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) and the True Skill Statistic (TSS). Values greater than 0.8 were considered indicative of good predictive performance, were minimal differences (<0.1) between evaluation and validation metrics were interpreted as evidence of low overfitting and temporal consistency. The final model (LightGBM or XGBoost), selected based on performance metrics, was fitted using data from 2023–2025 for imported dengue cases and data from 2015–2025 for *Ae. aegypti* (Tables 4–7).
5. Post-analysis and prediction. Variable importance was evaluated, and spatial projections were generated for 2023 and 2024 (Figure 1–2). Continuous probability surfaces were produced at a 100 m resolution, representing the likelihood of suitable conditions for vector presence or imported dengue cases.

Hyperparameter Space.

Preliminary Models

Table 1. Hyperparameter space in machine learning algorithms with the datasets of presence and pseudo-absence of imported cases (2023 & 2024) of dengue and *Ae. aegypti* (2015–2024).

Hyperparameter	Dengue 2023			Dengue 2024			Ae. aegypti		
	Range	LightGBM	XGBoost	Range	LightGBM	XGBoost	Range	LightGBM	XGBoost
columns	NA	18	19	NA	20	21	NA	19	20
rows	NA	324	263	NA	600	473	NA	181	159
mtry	4 a 6	4	4	4 a 6	4	4	3–7	6	3
trees	100 a 500	124	237	100 a 500	419	483	100 a 600	541	104
tree_depth	3 a 5	4	4	3 a 5	4	3	3–7	6	6
loss_reduction	-3.0 a 1.0	0.0167	0.0070	-3.0 a 1.0	0.0030	0.0453	Model defined	0.111	0.01126
learning_rate	-2.0 a 0.5	0.0390	0.0840	-2.0 a 0.5	0.1370	0.0111	Model defined	6.73e-10	2.47e-6

Final Models

Table 2. Hyperparameter space in machine learning algorithms with the datasets of presence and pseudo-absence of imported cases of dengue (2023–2025) and *Ae. aegypti* (2015–2025) in the final models.

Hyperparameter	Dengue 2015–2025			Ae. aegypti 2015–2025		
	Range	LightGBM	XGBoost	Range	LightGBM	XGBoost
columns	NA	18	21	NA	18	21
rows	NA	191	191	NA	191	191
mtry	4 a 6	4	4	3–7	4	4
trees	100 a 500	172	172	100 a 600	383	383
tree_depth	3 a 5	5	5	3–7	5	5
loss_reduction	-3.0 a 1.0	0.0870	0.0870	Model defined	0.220	0.220
learning_rate	-2.0 a 0.5	0.0115	0.0115	Model defined	2.84	2.84

Internal and external evaluation

XGBoost and LightGBM

Table 3. Performance metrics of LightGBM and XGBoost models across validation schemes and climate datasets.

Year	Metrics	LightGBM						XGBoost					
		Bioclim + Climate			Current Climate			Bioclim + Climate			Current Climate		
		Validation		External	Validation		External	Validation		External	Validation		External
		Internal	train		Internal	test		Internal	test		Internal	test	
Dengue													
2023	accuracy	0.94	0.94	0.89	0.97	0.92	0.83	0.94	0.94	0.91	0.92	0.91	0.82
2023	sensitivity	0.96	0.95	0.96	0.97	0.95	0.95	0.93	0.95	0.94	0.94	0.95	0.93
2023	bci	0.90	0.95	**0.76**	0.90	0.92	0.84	0.96	0.99	0.98	0.94	0.96	0.90
2023	tss	0.89	0.87	**0.71**	0.95	0.83	**0.58**	0.87	0.87	**0.78**	0.83	**0.79**	**0.56**
Dengue													
2024	accuracy	0.99	0.92	0.93	0.99	0.94	**0.68**	0.97	0.92	0.93	0.98	0.95	**0.74**
2024	sensitivity	0.98	0.93	0.92	0.98	0.95	**0.48**	0.97	0.93	0.92	0.97	0.95	**0.59**
2024	bci	0.87	0.63	**0.60**	0.94	0.99	**0.76**	0.98	0.95	0.90	0.98	0.87	0.95
2024	tss	0.97	0.84	0.87	0.97	0.88	**0.48**	0.95	0.84	0.86	0.96	0.90	**0.59**

XGBoost

Table 4. Performance metrics across evaluation schemes using bioclim plus current climatic data.

Year	Metrics	Evaluation					
		Internal		External			
		Train	Test	2023	2024	2025	
Dengue							
2023	AUC		0.98	0.98	-	0.97	0.95
2023	TSS		0.87	0.87	-	0.78	0.81
2023	Sensitivity		0.93	0.95	-	0.94	0.93
2023	BCI		0.96	0.99	-	0.98	0.92
2023	BS		0.05	0.05	-	0.07	0.07
Dengue							
2024	AUC		0.99	0.97	0.97	-	0.96
2024	TSS		0.95	0.84	0.86	-	0.89
2024	Sensitivity		0.97	0.93	0.92	-	0.93
2024	BCI		0.98	0.95	0.90	-	0.93
2024	BS		0.02	0.05	0.06	-	0.06

Ae. aegypti

XGBoost and LightGBM

Table 5. Internal and external evaluation of *Ae. aegypti* using XGBoost and LightGBM with only bioclim, bioclim

Hyper	Valor	Datos	Year	Metrics	LightGBM						
					Bioclim + Climate			Current Climate			
					Validation		External	Validation		External	
					Internal	train		Internal	test		
filtro = TRUE											
mtry =	3-7	1 cell	2024	accuracy	0.98	0.96	1.00	0.99	0.98	1.00	**1.0
tree =	100-600	p =buff 200	2024	**sensitivity**	0.96	0.93	1.00	0.99	0.97	1.00	**1.0
tree_depth =	3-7	pa =buff 2200	2024	**bci**	**0.45**	**0.58**	**1.00**	**0.73**	**1.00**	NA	0.9
filtro	**TRUE**	n = 143	2024	tss	0.96	0.93	**1.00**	0.99	0.97	**1.00**	**1.0
filtro = FALSE											
mtry =	3-7	1 cell	2024	accuracy	0.95	0.93	**0.78**	0.94	0.94	**0.78**	**1.0
tree =	100-600	p =buff 200	2024	**sensitivity**	0.99	0.93	0.83	0.98	0.93	0.83	**1.0
tree_depth =	3-7	pa =buff 2200	2024	**bci**	0.82	0.93	0.89	**0.71**	0.93	**0.80**	0.9
filtro	**FALSE**	n = 143	2024	tss	0.94	0.86	**0.61**	0.92	0.87	**0.60**	**1.0

LightGBM

Table 6. Internal and external evaluation of *Ae. aegypti* using LightGBM with only bioclim, bioclim plus current climatic data and buffer distance (0, 200, 400 and 600)

Hyper	Valor	Datos	Year	Metrics	LightGBM						
					Bioclim + Climate			Current Climate			
					Validation		External	Validation		External	
					Internal	train		Internal	test		
mtry =	3-7	1 cell		AUC	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
tree =	100-600	**p =buff 0**		TSS	0.96	0.93	1.00	0.99	0.97	1.00	1.00
tree_depth =	3-7	pa =buff 2200	2024	Sensitivity	0.96	0.93	1.00	0.99	0.97	1.00	1.00
filtro	TRUE	n = 143		BCI	0.45	0.58	1.00	0.73	1.00	1.00	1.00
				BS	0.02	0.03	0.00	0.01	0.02	NA	NA
mtry =	3-7	1 cell		AUC	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
tree =	100-600	**p =buff 200**		TSS	0.98	0.96	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00
tree_depth =	3-7	pa =buff 2200	2024	Sensitivity	0.98	0.96	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00
filtro	TRUE	n = 143		BCI	0.94	0.55	1.00	1.00	0.48	1.00	1.00
				BS	0.01	0.03	1.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00
mtry =	3-7	1 cell		AUC	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
tree =	100-600	**p =buff 400**		TSS	0.95	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
tree_depth =	3-7	pa =buff 2200	2024	Sensitivity	0.97	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
filtro	TRUE	n = 143		BCI	0.67	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
				BS	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
mtry =	3-7	1 cell		AUC	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
tree =	100-600	**p =buff 600**		TSS	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
tree_depth =	3-7	pa =buff 2200	2024	Sensitivity	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
filtro	TRUE	n = 143		BCI	0.43	1.00	NA	0.93	0.95	0.93	0.93
				BS	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04

Final models

Table 7. Evaluation of the final models of the imported case and *Ae. aegypti* dataset.

Dataset	ML algorithm	Period	Sensitivity		AUC		TSS		Niche Overlap		
			Train	Test	Train	Test	Train	Test	Partial ROC ¹	Schoener's D	Hellinger's I
Dengue	XGBoost	2023–2025	0.95	0.95	0.99	0.97	0.92	0.87	1.1	0.75	0.79
<i>Ae. aegypti</i>	LightGBM	2015–2025	0.98	0.96	1.00	1.00	0.97	0.96	1.2		

Variable Importance Scores

Imported dengue cases presence

Figure 1. Variable importance scores for the predictors of imported dengue cases presence with XGBoost

Ae. aegypti presence

Figure 2. Variable importance scores for the predictors of *Ae. aegypti* presence with LightGBM